

Causes and Consequences of Dropout in Vocational High Schools and Suggestions for Prevention

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Abstract

Dropout is a global educational problem that affects individuals, families, and communities, and has far-reaching consequences for society. The causes of dropout are multi-faceted and vary widely across individuals and contexts. In vocational high schools, dropout rates are particularly concerning due to the unique challenges faced by students in these schools. Preventing dropout in vocational high schools requires a multifaceted approach, including early identification and intervention, targeted academic and career support, mentoring and counselling, and family and community engagement. This study aims to discuss the causes and consequences of the risk of early leaving in vocational high schools and what needs to be done to prevent early leaving based on literature research. Based on this study, it can be suggested that promoting family and peer support, addressing mental health issues, addressing substance abuse, providing academic support, improving the school environment, providing financial support, and addressing early marriage may decrease the school dropout. These measures can help create a positive school environment that fosters academic achievement, inclusivity, and community and can ultimately prevent dropout.

Keywords: *School dropout, causes of school dropout, vocational high school.*

Introduction

The term "school dropout" lacks a universally accepted definition, with some researchers defining it as not enrolling in school after reaching the compulsory school age, while others define it as discontinuing school for two consecutive weeks in one term. School dropout is a common global educational problem, with UNICEF data indicating that nearly 142 million upper secondary students are left out of the educational system (UNICEF, 2016). The leading school dropout causative factors can be classified as individual, economic, socio-cultural, and institutional. Factors such as low income, socio-cultural variables, and institutional variables like teacher-school relationships and academic failure are linked to school dropout rates.

School dropout is a complex issue that has been a topic of concern for educators, policymakers, and parents for many years (Berlin, Furstenberg Jr. & Water, 2010). Dropout refers to the act of leaving school before completing a course of study or obtaining a diploma or degree (Lamb & Markussen, 2011). It is a problem that affects individuals, families, and communities, and has far-reaching consequences for society. Dropout rates vary widely across different regions and types of schools, with vocational high schools being particularly susceptible to high rates of dropout.

The causes of dropout are multi-faceted and vary widely across individuals and contexts (Shaihdul & Karim, 2015). Some common reasons for dropout include academic difficulties, socio-economic factors, family and personal problems, lack of motivation, and inadequate support systems. To understand the complex nature of dropout, several models have been proposed to explain the process of disengagement from school. These models include the push-out, pull-out, and falling-out models, among others.

Dropout rates are a significant concern, as they have implications for the future success of individuals and the well-being of communities (Jordan, Kostandini & Mykerezi, 2012). Dropout rates vary widely across different types

of schools, with vocational high schools experiencing higher rates of dropout than other types of schools. This is a cause for concern, as vocational education can be a pathway to employment and economic security for many students.

Dropout in vocational high schools has unique challenges and consequences (Tas, Selvitopu, Bora & Demirkaya, 2013). Vocational high schools offer students training in specific trades or professions, with the goal of preparing them for the workforce. However, students in vocational high schools face a range of challenges that can contribute to dropout, such as academic difficulties, lack of support, and limited career opportunities. Furthermore, the consequences of dropout in vocational high schools can be severe, as students may not have the skills or credentials needed to compete in the job market.

Preventing dropout in vocational high schools requires a multifaceted approach (Schargel & Smink, 2013). Educators, policymakers, and community members must work together to create supportive environments that promote academic success and career readiness. Strategies for prevention may include early identification and intervention for students at risk of dropout, targeted academic and career support, mentoring and counselling, and family and community engagement. Additionally, addressing the root causes of dropout, such as poverty and inequality, is essential for creating long-term solutions.

Dropout in vocational high schools is a significant challenge that has far-reaching consequences for individuals, families, and communities (Farias & Sevilla, 2015). Understanding the causes and consequences of dropout, as well as developing effective prevention strategies, is essential for creating a more equitable and prosperous society. By working together to support students in vocational high schools, we can ensure that all young people can reach their full potential and contribute to the world around them. In this context, in this study, the causes and consequences of the risk of early leaving in vocational high schools and what needs to be done to prevent early leaving are discussed in the light of literature research.

1. School Dropout

School dropout rates are a crucial indicator of a country's education conditions. High dropout rates signal insufficient or problematic education systems, with students discontinuing their education prematurely. Though the term "school dropout" encompasses all educational levels, it generally refers to stages up to university (primary, middle, and high school) but can also apply to university students (Taylı, 2008)

School dropout is a complex issue, affected by individual and societal factors. Even though mandatory education periods have increased, and schooling has become more widespread, the problem is far from being completely resolved (Cullen, 2000). School dropout has economic and cultural implications, as it negatively impacts students' lifelong development and social integration. Dropout rates can lead to issues such as unemployment, crime rates, low quality of life, and low-income levels (Taş, Selvitopu, Bora & Demirkaya, 2013).

To create a more educated and skilled demographic, it is essential to address school dropout rates, particularly during high school years. Prevention efforts should not only focus on the individual but also tackle economic and social problems leading to dropout (Özer, Gençtarım & Ergene, 2011). School dropout is a pressing educational issue in developed countries, and efforts are being made to reduce it. However, focusing on assigning blame rather than finding solutions is counterproductive. Identifying the root causes of dropout is necessary to effectively address the problem (Beyhan & Dalgıç, 2012).

2. Reasons of Dropout

There are several factors that contribute to students dropping out of school, which should be examined individually. These reasons include migration, economic problems, family issues, peer relationships, and relationships with teachers and the school (Şimşek, 2011). One key predictor of school dropout is academic achievement, with low-performing students at higher risk. Additionally, absenteeism due to low academic achievement can lead to school dropout (Aküzüm et al, 2015).

School dropout reasons are complex and not solely based on individual desires. Factors pushing students out of school include social and physical conditions of the school, personal characteristics, and economic insufficiencies (Bayhan & Bilgiç, 2012). Another predictor of school dropout is economic issues, especially for students from low socioeconomic backgrounds who may need to work instead of attending school (Özer, Gençtarım & Ergene, 2011). Early marriages, particularly in some countries, contribute to school dropout rates among girls, often happening against their will (Koçtürk, Bilge & Yüksel, 2018).

Migration, family education, and cultural situations also play a significant role in the risk of school dropout (Taylı, 2016). Parents' education level is a major variable, with students of highly educated parents less likely to be absent and more likely to have supportive, motivating parents. Problematic family relationships and conditions can also contribute to school dropout (Aküzüm et al, 2015). Additionally, negative social circumstances, such as poor peer relationships, social incompatibility, and disconnection from the school, can lead to dropping out. Issues with school accessibility, quality of education, school environment, overcrowded classrooms, unsuitable teaching methods, and security problems can also cause students to leave school (Şahin, Arseven & Kılıç, 2016)

Reasons of school dropout are examined in several academic studies. Şimşek (2011) conducted with high school students in Southeast Anatolia region found that dropping out of school was affected by personal and family characteristics, the education system, school, and teachers. Özer, Gençtarım ve Ergene (2011) studied with high school students in Ankara and revealed that family and peer support reduced the risk of dropping out, while impulsive behaviors, alcohol and tobacco use, and antisocial behaviors increased the risk. Bayhan ve Dalgıç (2012) focused on the experiences of 25 high school students in Kocaeli who had dropped out of school and started vocational education, and found that academic failure, lack of interest in school, dislike of school, absenteeism, disciplinary problems, and health issues were the main reasons for dropping out. Aküzüm et al (2015) investigated the causes of absenteeism and school dropout

among primary school students and found that lack of parental sensitivity, economic problems, and inadequate technical facilities at schools were the main causes. Zorbaz (2018) studied with high school students in Ankara and identified that working outside of school, having friends who dropped out, exhibiting antisocial behaviors, and feeling alienated from school increased the risk of dropping out, while academic monitoring, school commitment, and parental involvement decreased the risk. Koçtürk, Bilge & Yüksel (2018) studied with early-married teenagers in Turkey and found that early marriage was also a cause of dropping out of school, along with poor academic performance and family problems. Boyacı & Öz (2018) associated academic demotivation with dropping out of school and found that academic achievement and absenteeism played a mediating role. Finally, studies conducted in Canada (Dupere et al, 2017), South Korea (Kim, Joo & Lee, 2018), Yemen (Mirza et al, 2018), and Norway (Kristensen, Corbett, Hanvold, Hoff & Mehlum, 2018) found that chronic life stressors, depression, school-related factors, hyperactivity, and mental health issues increased the risk of dropping out of school.

Dupere et al (2017) studied with 545 high school students from Canada and showed that those at risk of dropping out were three times more likely to be exposed to chronic life stressors compared to average students. Dupere et al (2018) found that one in four students who dropped out had significant clinical depression symptoms in the three months prior to leaving school. Factors such as school size, teacher-student ratio, and academic achievement were found to be significantly related to the risk of dropping out in Kim, Joo & Lee's (2018) study. In Mirza et al.'s (2018) study of Yemeni children, it was found that hyperactivity, school failure, behavioral disorders, and parental separation were associated with an increased risk of dropping out. Dropping out of school was found to increase the risk of drug-related deaths in Norway, while a positive teacher-student relationship was found to reduce the risk of dropping out for students with mental health problems in Norway, as concluded by Kristen et al (2018) and Holen, Waaktar & Sagatun (2018). Other studies (Rud, Klaveren, Groot & van den Brink, 2018; Guio, Choi &

Escardibul, 2018; Tabuchi, Fujihara, Shinozaki & Fukuhara, 2018; Gil, Antelm-Lanzat, Cacheior-Gonzalez & Perez-Navio, 2018; Ithzaki, 2018) found that poor academic performance and factors such as absenteeism, smoking addiction, and abuse were related to dropping out of school. Finally, Stoner et al (2019) found that teenage pregnancy was both a cause and consequence of dropping out of school for young women, and recommended prevention efforts targeted at this group in South Africa.

3. School Dropout Models

Various models have been developed in the literature regarding school dropout. The main models are the General Deviance Model, Deviant Affiliation Model, School Socialization Theory, Poor Family Socialization Theory, and Structural Strains Theory. *The General Deviance Model* explores the relationship between dropout behavior and deviant behaviors leading to dropout, such as alcohol, tobacco, and substance use. This model suggests a significant relationship between academic failure, deviant behaviors, and school dropout. Early sexual activity and pregnancy can also affect academic achievement and lead to dropout (Manona, 2015).

The Deviant Affiliation Model posits that students who drop out often have close friends who are also at risk of dropping out, displaying deviant behaviors, and having low future expectations (Taylı, 2008). *The School Socialization Theory* highlights the role of structural features and school climate in students' academic failure, with factors such as teacher and administrator indifference, unfair behavior, and a violent school environment leading to dropout (Taylı, 2008). *The Poor Family Socialization Theory* emphasizes the impact of parents' low education levels, prior school dropout, and lack of support for their children's education on dropout rates (Manona, 2015). *The Structural Strains Theory* focuses on students' demographic and structural characteristics, suggesting that minority status, belonging to a certain ethnic group, being male, or having low socioeconomic status can contribute to dropping out of school (Manona, 2015).

4. Dropout Rates

The most important indicators of access to education are enrolment rates and upper secondary graduate level. When looking at Table 1, the net enrolment rate at the primary school level was 98.2% as of the end of 2022. At the secondary school level, this rate was 89.8%, while it is 89,7% at the upper secondary education. On the other hand, the enrolment rate of girls is equal to that of boys at the primary school level, but it is lower than that of boys at the secondary and high school levels. Overall, the percentages of students who have completed their primary school, lower secondary school, and upper secondary education have been increasing steadily over the years. In each educational year, the percentage of female students who have completed their education has been slightly higher than the percentage of male students. The percentage of students who have completed their upper secondary education is lower than the percentage of students who have completed their primary school and lower secondary school, especially in the most recent years. There is a significant drop in the percentage of students who have completed their lower secondary education in 2020-2021 compared to the previous years, possibly due to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on education. However, this percentage has increased again in 2021-2022.

Table 1: Net Enrolment Rate in Turkey

Educational Year	Primary school			Lower secondary school			Upper secondary education		
	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
2017-2018	91,5	91,4	91,7	94,5	94,3	94,7	83,6	83,8	83,4
2018-2019	91,9	91,8	92,1	93,3	92,9	93,6	84,2	84,5	83,9
2019-2020	93,6	93,7	93,5	95,9	95,7	96,1	85,0	85,2	84,9
2020-2021	93,2	93,3	93,1	88,9	89,0	88,7	87,9	88,1	87,8
2021-2022	93,2	93,2	93,1	89,8	90,0	89,7	89,7	90,0	89,3

Source: Turkish Statistical Institute

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Table 2 shows Upper Secondary Graduation Rates for OECD countries, as well as the rates for people separately where available. Some notable results which can be seen from the Table 2 is that Korea has the highest secondary school graduation rate of men, with 96.67%. Chile, Slovenia, and Israel also have very high rates, all above 89%. Brazil and the United Kingdom have the lowest graduation rates of men, with 55.78% and 57.20% respectively. In most countries, women have higher graduation rates than men. This is particularly noticeable in Slovenia, where the women's rate is almost 5% higher than the men's rate, and in Portugal, where the women's rate is almost 8% higher than the men's rate. There is significant variation in graduation rates across different countries, with rates ranging from 55.78% in Brazil to 96.67% in Korea. However, most countries have graduation rates in the range of 70-90%.

Table 2: Upper Secondary Graduation Rate of OECD Countries (2020 or latest available)

Latest	Men	Women	Latest	Men	Women
Austria	79,41	86,31	Latvia	81,98	90,58
Belgium	74,25	83,66	Lithuania	82,53	90,42
Brazil	55,78	65,14	Luxembourg	77,55	85,05
Canada	84,03	87,50	Mexico	63,22	72,65
Chile	90,92	96,06	Netherlands	81,75	91,85
Colombia	70,43	80,21	New Zealand	79,76	84,44
Costa Rica	69,57	80,66	Norway	81,82	89,75
Czech Republic	85,26	84,39	OECD - Average	79,34	85,87
Denmark	75,50	83,72	Poland	82,14	86,59
Estonia	75,27	83,94	Portugal	85,96	93,71
Finland	79,96	87,42	Slovak Republic	77,11	79,09
Germany	68,94	70,73	Slovenia	89,46	94,64
Greece	87,89	93,25	Spain	78,23	87,71
Hungary	77,41	79,38	Sweden	71,21	76,47
Iceland	69,09	87,96	Switzerland	85,08	88,00
Israel	86,73	93,36	Türkiye	79,09	83,74
Italy	87,91	92,36	United Kingdom	57,20	68,20
Korea	96,67	96,40	United States	84,21	89,44

Source : <https://data.oecd.org/students/secondary-graduation-rate.htm>

5. Drop-out in Vocational High Schools

There are 4640 vocational high schools in Turkey, serving around 1.8 million students and providing training in 228 different professional fields (MoNE, 2018). After completing primary and secondary education, students can study at vocational high schools, which offer a four-year education consisting of a common national curriculum, courses relevant to the vocational field, specialization, and an apprenticeship program. Vocational high school graduates can either continue their

education at polytechnic colleges or pursue a four-year tertiary education by passing a university entrance exam (MoNE, 2018).

Turkey has made significant efforts to improve technical and vocational education and training (TVET) at the high school level by developing occupational standards, launching curriculum reform, and focusing on the digital transformation. The country has recognized the importance of adapting vocational education to Industry 4.0, and as a result, the role of teachers has become even more important in adapting to the changing economic and industrial system. However, challenges such as student indifference, discipline issues, lack of physical facilities, and intense education programs have been identified as dropout reasons in vocational high schools (Ayaz & Özdemir, 2021).

Turkey, like other countries, experiences school dropout issues, with studies indicating that female students have a higher tendency to drop out than male students (Caner, Guven, Okten & Sakallı, 2016; Cemalcılar & Gökçen, 2014). Students with Arabic and Kurdish ethnic origins also demonstrate a higher school dropout tendency than those with Turkish origin (Kırdar, 2019). Factors such as family and friends' support, disciplinary issues, alcohol and tobacco usage, and anti-social behavior impact school dropout rates in Turkey. Research has also shown that school dropout is related to the educational system, school facilities, socio-cultural factors, and economic circumstances.

School dropout in Turkey is related to economic, socio-cultural, institutional, and individual variables. The Ministry of National Education (MoNE, 2018) indicated that the school dropout ratio is higher among vocational religious high schools and vocational high schools compared to general middle schools. This finding highlights the need to discuss and question the role of vocational schools in dropout rates, which could inform future educational policy.

Vocational schools in Turkey aim to prepare students for job fields and professions and to prepare them for higher education. However, students who fail to attend academic high schools are often forwarded to vocational high schools, which primarily serve poor students. This results in students from poor and poor

backgrounds being deprived of the opportunity for higher education and employment.

As concluded by Taş, Bora, Selvitopu and Demirkaya (2013), reasons of dropout in vocational high schools can be categorized four sub-themes: individual, school, family, and neighbourhood-based factors. Individual reasons included absenteeism, grade repetition, intensive curriculum, and reluctance to attend school. School and neighbourhood factors encompassed the remoteness of school, mistrust of the neighbourhood, and teacher repression. Family-based reasons for dropout were mainly the socio-economic level of the family and poverty.

Yorgun (2014) conducted a study that involved three different groups of students: a group of 24 students who lived in Hatay and had dropped out of school in the past two years, a group of 454 students who lived in Izmir and had switched from formal education to open high school, and a group of 906 students attending three different types of high schools in Izmir. The study found that based on the data on the risk of dropping out of school, male students had a higher risk than female students, students with lower academic achievement had a higher risk than those with higher achievement, students with more siblings and less family support and involvement had a higher risk of dropping out of school.

Özger (2019) found that students have a medium level of risk for dropping out of school, with the highest risk being in the "Self-Withdrawal" subscale. Male students from vocational high school had a moderate risk for dropping out, particularly in the "Attitudes of the Peer Group to School" subscale. Parental education level had the highest effect on dropout risk in the "Self-Withdrawal" dimension, with students whose parents had only completed primary school having a moderate risk. Students with a lower grade average or higher absenteeism had a moderate risk for dropping out, particularly in the "Attitudes of Peer Group to School" subscale. This shows that male vocational high school students who have low academic achievement and negative peer attitudes and whose parents have low educational level have a high risk of dropping out.

Çetin (2019) conducted a study that the risk of dropping out of school for vocational and technical Anatolian high school students differs significantly from students attending other types of schools. Students attending vocational and technical Anatolian high school have a higher risk of dropping out of school compared to students attending science or Anatolian high schools. Besides, the risk of dropping out of high school for students varies significantly based on whether they repeat a grade during their educational process. Students who repeat a grade have a higher risk of dropping out of school.

Conclusion

The issue of school dropout is complex and multifaceted, but there are steps that can be taken to address it. Based on the literature review, the following suggestions could be implemented.

Family and peer support: Encouraging families and friends to be involved in students' education can help reduce the risk of dropping out. This could include parent-teacher conferences, family involvement in school activities, and mentoring programs.

Addressing mental health: Identifying and treating depression and other mental health issues can help prevent dropout. Providing access to counselling services and resources for mental health support could be beneficial.

Addressing substance abuse: Addressing tobacco and alcohol use as well as other substance abuse can be important to prevent dropping out. Programs that educate students about the risks of substance abuse and provide support for those struggling with addiction could be helpful.

Academic support: Providing academic support and intervention for struggling students could help prevent academic failure and dropout. This could include tutoring, mentoring programs, and academic enrichment programs.

Improved school environment: Creating a positive school environment that fosters academic achievement, inclusivity, and community can help prevent dropout. This

could include measures such as smaller class sizes, increased teacher-student ratio, and implementing anti-bullying programs.

Financial support: Addressing economic issues that prevent students from attending school, such as lack of resources, can help prevent dropout. Providing financial support for families in need could help ensure that students can attend school regularly.

Addressing early marriage: Addressing the issue of early marriage and providing support for young parents could help prevent dropout among this group.

By implementing these strategies, schools and communities can help reduce the risk of dropping out and ensure that students have the support and resources they need to succeed in school.

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